

COMPARISON OF THE SOCIAL CAPITAL, LIFE SATISFACTION, ACHIEVEMENT PERCEPTION AND EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE LEVEL OF THE VOLUNTEERS AND NON-VOLUNTEERSⁱ

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Abstract:

The purpose of this research is to compare the level of Volunteers' and Non Volunteers' Social Capital, Life Satisfaction, Achievement Perception and Emotional Intelligence. Sampling group consists of 208 Search and Rescue Team (AKUT) volunteers and 138 non volunteers. The questionnaire form was consisted of demographic variables and Social Capital Scale developed by Onyx and Bullen (2000) and adapted into Turkish by Ardahan (2012), Achievement Perception Scale developed by Bilgin and Kaynak (2008), Life Satisfaction Scale developed by Diener et al (1985) and adapted into Turkish by Köker (1991), Emotional Intelligence Scale developed by Schutte et al (2006) and then applied by Chan (2004, 2006). In the process of assessing data, the descriptive statistic methods, Independent Samples Test (t) have been used and results have been assessed according to significant level 0.05. As a result of this study; it was found that there are statistically meaningful differences in life style and leisure preferences between AKUT Volunteer' and Non Volunteers' in terms of Social Capital, Life Satisfaction, Achievement Perception, and Emotional Intelligence level.

Keywords: AKUT, life satisfaction, social capital, achievement perception, emotional intelligence, volunteers, non-volunteers

1. The Concepts of AKUT and Voluntariness

After 1990s, nature sports in Turkey started to be in demand so much and by being depending on this, accidents and events such as disappearing increased as well. Reaching to person/persons and living beings in need in the events encountered in the

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nature and doing emergency action require special equipment, availability of persons having adequate mental, physical, knowledge and psychological competence and efficient management of this process. When required, it also needs agility of the teams that shall do "search" and "rescue" to be able to deploy to the venue by becoming organized at the moment of hearing the event with the competence and equipment to be able to conduct search and rescue processes to the end (Ardahan, 2015a).

With this purpose, Search Rescue used to be done mostly through fire department until the establishment of the first team. But, while it was supposed to have the organizing in professional format, first organization in Turkey was formed in the 1996 as non-governmental organization (NGO) with the name of Search Rescue Association – AKUT (<http://www.akut.org.tr/tarihce>) completely on the basis of volunteering in order to realize the mission "in order to reach the persons in trouble within the shortest time in the events of getting lost and accidents in mountain and natural conditions, in the natural disasters such as earthquake, flood and in the big accidents by completely being volunteered, with amateur work and professional approach, to create the required conditions for help by doing correct research and rescue work and to provide their transfers to secure ambient conditions after providing basic first aid support to the survivors, to minimize the loss of lives in this kind of events and to give information to community in the subjects of research and rescue".

There are two different search rescue team in AKUT depending on the level of expertise. The first one of them is Mountain Search Rescue Team and there are three requirements for an individual to take place in this team. These are; a) to be mountaineer, b) to achieve competence in the trainings and practices and c) to have suitable personality and mission to the mission of AKUT. Individuals having trainings depending on the area of expertise one to one and these are generally about flood, fire and earthquake trainings. At the end of the trainings, a participant showing the competence of "c" clause from being in Mountain Search Rescue Team can take place in AKUT Urban Operation Team (AKUT KOE) (Ardahan, 2015a).

"The feeling of helping to the others and philanthropy" brought by living with the others and burdened to the individuals as one of the many responsibilities is rewarded in many societies and religions and showed as the correct way of behavior (Aktepe, 2014; Uşd, 2014). Individuals can carry this philanthropy behavior to dimension of volunteerism alone by themselves or by getting organized with the others for the elders, disabled persons, women exposed to violence, children in disadvantageous region. These may happen in many situations from education, living beings with their breeds under the thread, illegal lumbering of forests, invasion of the green areas, glacial melting up to illegal whaling. While helping is more of an individual behavior, individuals coming together with the others for similar purposes and they may want to realize philanthropy behavior outlast and institutionalize through a non-governmental organization (NGO) (Ardahan, 2015a). Even though volunteerism and philanthropy are mostly used as synonyms, they are two different attitude and behavior from each other. In order to have volunteerism behavior in an

individual, "philanthropy" value, attitude and behavior must exist. Philanthropy is one of the most basic values/bases having influence in the formation of volunteerism behavior (Clary et al., 1998). While philanthropy is generally a short-term spontaneous behavior repeated a few times, volunteerism is sustained during life (Clary and Snyder, 1999).

Volunteerism has many definitions. Most common definition of volunteerism; without having the expectation for any material return and/or benefit, is assuming any mission individually and/or with the others without having force or any authorization or the others in the free times of the individuals and in the circumstances/events which are believed to be correct to increase the quality of life of the persons other the family and immediate vicinity to be useful for the community in the way to create positive added value (STGM, 2006; Ardahan, 2015a). When volunteerism is defined this way, non-volunteering can be defined as not participating in any activity by the individual by volunteering the same, to give up being volunteer for any reason and/or participating in volunteerism actions with the expectation of material return and/or benefit. Just like in volunteerism, there may be a need to stress the differences not to mix non-volunteering situation with not being philanthropist. Individual can be philanthropist but he cannot be in the activity by volunteering. Together with this, individual may not be philanthropist of volunteer (Ardahan, 2015b). AKUT's establishment purpose also complies with all definitions taking place in the volunteerism definition of the volunteers in AKUT Urban Operation Team (AKUT KOE) for them to take place within this scope and to be in volunteerism activity and to continue the same (Ardahan, 2015a).

There are factors that have influence on the individual to be volunteer or not to be volunteer or to give up from being volunteer. Along with the ones who defend that factors having influence on the individual to be volunteer are derived from individual's behavior is related his personality (Crandall, 1980) and in addition to this, behavior is originated from the social structure and conditions where individual takes place other than the personality (Levy, 1979), there are some scholars like Stebbins (1996) who defend personal factors and social factors, some others like Wymer et al., (1996) who defend personal factors, social determinants and the power or being useful and these factors have influence in being volunteer. Ardahan (2010a, 2010b) and Koşan and Güneş (2009) have indicated that "purposive motives" which can be useful in the current community, to live group interaction, "social motives" such as creating social relations and integration and to wear the dress of an NGO or organization, to carry the coat of arms of the same and to belong to it and "material based motives" such as being materially awarded have influence in being volunteer and sustaining the same. Along with these, volunteering is also explained with motivation theories. Inner and external motivation taken in hand in The Self-Determination Theory (Deci ve Ryan, 1985), Purpose and Duty Focused Approach defined in The Achievement Goal Theory (Pintrich, 2000), in The Activity Theory, it is defended that individuals must continuously be in an active life (Engeström et al. 2003) and Maslow's The Need

Theory-NT "Belonging", "Respectability" and "Self-Realization" needs (Ibrahim and Cordes, 2002) have influence in volunteerism (Ardahan, 2015a).

In literature, even if volunteerism is accepted as an activity done by the individuals in their leisure times, the reasons and way of being in AKUT, (for the individuals) AKUT KOE are different from the volunteerism reasons and ways participating in the other volunteerism activities. While volunteerism is a leisure activity, AKUT volunteers do this as serious leisure time activity (Ardahan, 2016). As the details can be seen in Ardahan's (2016) work, AKUT volunteers are not in AKUT because of the reasons in order to get away from the family, friend environment, daily responsibilities and routine, to become socialized, to be happy, to have nice time, to belong to a group, to be appreciated by the others and to be together with the friends from work/school and social world. The reasons of the individuals to be in AKUT are formed from very high-level social values away from the personal ego. In "Validity Reliability of Motivating Factors Scale Work of Ardahan (2015a) interrogating why the individuals are volunteered to AKUT". Author has discovered that the factors motivating the individual to become volunteer are the factors taking place in the headings of "Approving A Mission", "Feeling Valuable/Succeeding", "Living the Volunteerism", "Exemplifying", "Renewal/To Be Renewed" and "Using the Skills/To Serve for the Purpose". Wilson (2000) and Levay (2014) have indicated that there were two kinds of benefits to be named as individual benefit and social benefit (created to the others) obtained in the activities voluntarily done by the individual. He has defined the benefits created for the individual himself as a) social interaction and becoming socially recognized, b) self-confidence, c) to create social relation/web with the others, d) improvement in physical, psychologic and mental health, e) low death rate, f) education/career output. On the other hand, the benefits created for the society are along with economic, social, physical dimensions, especially to keep the hopes of living and to be able to produce permanent/temporary support to them. In other words, created social benefit is the total of the effort of the individual to create the world defined by the individual also for the others partially or totally. With these dimensions, it is important for the individuals taking place in AKUT KOE to prefer a life focused on social benefit instead of personal benefit.

In the study of Wymer et al., (1996) named as Contextual Obstacles, factors which cause the individual not being the volunteer or not to continue being volunteer were taken. In addition to this, it has been put forward in the studies that not having enough free time by the individuals for the volunteerism or not having these times during the stage of giving up by having previously (Clary et al., 1994), having the individual with inadequate physical, emotional and mental condition (Fischer and Schaffer, 1993), receiving negative or no answer from the place applied for being volunteer (Rubin and Thorelli, 1984), negativities of the existing conditions as well as the ones encountered in the volunteered place, not being able to find the expectations by the person were also put forward in the studies related to the subject as the factors having influence in order not to be the volunteer (Ardahan, 2011). Subject has been

interrogated in Ardahan's (2015b) study of "Validity Reliability of Motivating Factors Scale Work" for the factors having influence on the individuals for them not to be volunteer or not to continue as volunteer and they were relived in the headings of "Inadequacy Belief and Negative Volunteerism Image", "Negative Volunteerism Experience", "Not Knowing How to Become the Volunteer", "Transportation Obstacle", "Believing That There Will Be Obstacle", "Poverty of Time" and "Contextual Obstacles".

2. Life Satisfaction

Despite of the fact that there are many factors motivating the individual to become the volunteer, the most important of them are the personality characteristics of the individual and the factors taken in hand and examined in all of the studies taking place in the literature having influence of the social context where individual takes places. Comparisons of the volunteered ones and not volunteered ones or the ones who gave up from volunteerism for any reason in their Social Capital (SC), Emotional Intelligence (EI), Achievement Perception (AP) and Living Satisfaction (LS) dimensions and interrogation of these values for their influence on becoming or not becoming the volunteer constitute the basis of this work.

Although satisfaction (satisfaction) concept has many forms such as economic satisfaction, vocational satisfaction, work satisfaction, social satisfaction, life satisfaction; the basic purpose of every person living is to fictionalize and live a life having high LS (Ardahan, 2014a). LS or with its other form "happiness" has always been the first thing for human beings to focus and both scientists and philosophers have seen the happiness expectation as the motivational resources of the individual's actions (Özer and Karabulut 2003). Satisfaction can be defined as individual's perception for life and his/her emotional response against this (Luthans, 1994) and at the same time, it can be defined as the criterion of meeting the expectations of the individuals as well (Schermerhorn at al., 1994). LS expresses the situation formed with the comparison of individual's life realized with his/her expectations and by being influenced from many numbers of factors, it expresses individual's state of being happy and state of being good by influencing many numbers of factors (Ardahan, 2014a). LS has the following important influences on individual's life; a) social, physical and economic structure together with the quality of the relationship fictionalized by the individual with his/her family, immediate vicinity and with the other individuals, b) his/her business life, family life, physical and mental health state, c) having his/her cultural and social life be satisfying, d) existence of his/her financial possibilities, e) possessed leisure time level and the quality of using it, f) his/her education life, g) current social status, h) individual's business, social relations and seeing himself/herself successful about the life, i) his/her spiritual life, and j) participation in the social life (Sirgy and Cornwell, 2002). In addition to these; k) instrumental comfort, l) having a child and childrearing, m) participating in State's local and national activities and public activities, n) being

working in a business, o) being learning, being able to understand himself/herself, having self-knowledge, p) reading books, listening music, going cinema, games etc. and to attend entertaining activities, r) socialization, s) to help the others and to look out for the others, t) personal confidence take place among the factors having influence on LS (Şahin 2008). Of course, some individuals make themselves happy. Some individuals take place in the activities voluntarily while some individuals prefer to do other factors in their own lives to make themselves happy and they increase LS accordingly. But, in order to realize a mission supported by the individual, it needs an endeavor and efforts and must be actively engaged in an activity for this and it causes advantages in the subject of LS for the individuals living this way.

3. Social Capital

One of the most important factors having effect on the individual's LS and whether or not being volunteer and empower the individual in a social world is the existence and quality of the social network developed by the individual with the society/community where individual takes place (Ardahan, 2014a). This network of relations is also named as Social Capital (SC) and while it is defined by Putnam et al. (1993), Fukuyama (1995, 1999) as "the characteristics of a community/group, total of the values owned by them", Kawachi et al. (1997) and Portes (1998) have seen SC not as the sum of the relations and values owned by the community or group, but they have expressed it by belonging to the individuals and as the values fictionalized among themselves. SC can be defined as the total of social relations and social organizations created by the trust, norm and social relations network of a group/community such as economic capital, physical capital, human capital, culture capital, health capital (Ardahan, 2012a) and at the same time it can be defined as the total of the social relations and social organizations created by confidence, norm and social network of a group/community (Putnam at al., 1993) and also as the contribution to social and economic life by the relations, institutions, values and behaviors establishing connection between the individuals (Grootaert and Van Bastelaer, 2002). Other than these definitions, SC is also defined as the ability of working together developed by the individuals alone or together with the others as the organizations structured formally/informally in order to be able to realize the common missions with these values existing in the individuals (Heral, 2006).

When it is observed from the point of these definitions, all kinds of volunteerism activity done by the individual alone or by together with the others in order to realize the same mission is the network of relationship forming/increasing SC. Two basic compounds of SC are the mutuality of created confidence, and the values created in the relations. While the feeling of confidence can be identified as the trust of the individual to the individual and reliability of the neighborhood lived in, there is the requirement to do the same by the members forming the community/group within mutual dependence and cooperation in order to form/sustain a healthy, satiated, meaningful life (Ardahan, 2014a). Creating the confidence environment needs the formation of selfless behaviors

and additional burden and responsibility to be assumed by the individuals voluntarily regardless of being in the living place, at work, on the street, in the restaurant went or within the family of between the individuals who know/do not know each other. Correspondingly, relations network based on confidence; shall have positive influence on productivity, profitability within the family, in social world and in the organizations (Cohen and Prusak, 2001; Smith, 1998).

SC value of the individual is measures with different approaches. Some of them have focus on economic outputs and social network characteristics of SC (Spellerberg, 1997; Putnam, 2000; Green et al., 2000; Hjøllund and Svendsen, 2000; Stone, 2001; Harper, 2002; Alanen and Niemelainen, 2003; Grootaert et al., 2004; Van der Gaag, 2005). In addition to these, the World Bank also measures SC with the dimensions of "solidarity and confidence", "acting together and partnership", "being a part of a group or network, "information and communication", "authorizing and political action" and "social coverage and dependence" (Ardahan, 2012a). Together with these, in the work developed by Onxy and Bullen in the year of (2000) by having its Turkish adaptation done by Ardahan (2012a) and also the measurement means used in the measurement of individuals' SC value in the existing study measures SC value of the individual with the dimensions of; a) "Participation to Local Committee" expressing the individual's participating in the local management formally/informally in order to have positive influence for the social dynamics and social life where individual takes place and/or to change the same b) "Non-governmental Organization (NGO) Membership" expressing individual's active role in the local management, c) "Social Representation" expressing the roles and responsibilities of the individual because of the reasons not in his/her direct responsibility but arising from the living paradigm of the individual, d) "Initiative in Social Issues" expressing individual's assumption for the other individuals in the community where individual lives and when needed expressing for the individual to take initiative to represent them in the social structure, e) "Safe Environment" expressing that individual finds the neighborhood, district where he/she lives in trustworthy and Safe Human expressing that individual trusts the people where he/she lives and in the social environment individual belongs, f) "Neighborhood Relation" expressing individual's neighborhood relationships fictionalized and realized with his/her neighbors in social scope, g) "Difference Tolerance" expressing individual's tolerance to individual differences such as culture, gender identity, life-style, religious values, h) "Belonging to A Place" expressing for the individual to see himself/herself belonging to where he/she works, educated school and to make himself/herself feel valuable (Ardahan, 2012a). All these factors consist of the elements having positive influence for the individual to become volunteer and for his/her LS as well (Ardahan, 2014a).

A life based on positive, meaningful and satiated social relations shows both individual's social cohesion with the others in the community he/she takes place, as well as the his/her reconciliation in the relations based on common values and belonging and this has positive influence on individual's LS and to become the

volunteer as well as SC (Putnam, 2001; Brown and Ferris, 2007; Wang and Graddy, 2008; Paik and Navarre-Jackson, 2011). Volunteerism can be personal and at the same time, it is also done more with the organized groups, in other words, with NGOs. SC measurement tools of "NGO Membership", "Participation to Local Management", "Taking Initiative in Social Issues", "Belonging to A Place" factors are the subjects which have direct relation with the volunteerism. Together with this, "Neighborhood Relation" corresponds to social cohesion and this is very much influenced from these relations in social context. Besides, even though "Tolerance to Difference" does not approve the differences such as religion, language, sub-culture, political opinion, gender, life-style, ethnic origin, it describes to be tolerant to the one who is not like himself and this is situation increasing the integration of the individual with the community he/she lives in. This situation shall provide individual to establish close communication and interaction as well as solidarity with the individuals who are not like him/her but supporting the same mission in volunteerism processes. As a matter of course, what SC and volunteerism have in common is the fact that they need relations based on confidence. All these factors also contain the factors that have positive influence on individual's LS.

4. Achievement Perception

Success is a definition that can take place in individual's art, work, sport, cultural life and at the same time, it can be in individual's social and business life. Success is a concept used not only to express a realized situation or a result reached but to explain the living paradigms, way of perception of personality structures and life fictionalized on the theory of living. When it is observed with these dimensions, in a situation, success can be defined as the realization of the defined objectives in a work or process by the individual/community/organization by using the resources efficiently and productively, to be able to show their selves and to challenge with the negativities (Ardahan, 2014b). As it is understood from this definition, the most basic reason for the life of the individual is the realization of the objectives defined by them or approved by them even if these are defined by the others with universal moral measurements by using the resources efficiently and productively (McClelland, 1985).

Volunteering can be taken in hand with the dimension of being in the activity of volunteerism with the Perception of Success (PS). In addition to this, Individuals having high success motive also increase their coping skills with the mental, physical and psychologic obstacles and difficulties met by them as well as the possibility to overcome the difficulties in the subject of performing qualified efforts in order to reach the determined objectives in their personal, social and professional lives by having high inner and external motivation. For this reason, in success motive; reaching the target, excellence, winning and feeling of inner winning come in sight in the lives of the individuals and they become identified with the objectives defined by them or approved by them even if these are defined by the others and this is an important factor

to increase their successes (Kaya and Selçuk, 2007). The key characteristic of the individuals having the desire of success is that they always improve themselves and they have the qualification to overcome the difficulties, they are determined, challenging, they do not give up easily, they always produce qualified efforts, they are the volunteers in assuming responsibility, they devote themselves to every subject when they define themselves within the desire of success, they do not need to be directed and audited by the others much, they work and live with plan (McClelland, 1961). In addition to these, having the individual see himself/herself successful shall directly influence individual's LS positively and this situation shall create synergy to the other areas as well. One of the most important reasons for the individual to give up volunteerism is not seeing himself/herself successful in the activity and/or having the feedback of inadequacy from the place of volunteering. Being unsuccessful in a work, duty and action is usually among the most important factors causing individuals give up. For this reason, it is important to have high SP in sustaining volunteerism and/or to have the feedback on this basis. Kaya and Selçuk (2007), Schuler and Prochaska (2001) have indicated that there were two basic factors for the individual or institutional success. First factor from these is ambitious, determined working, self-confidence and inner motivation related to the work and the second factors are defined as follows: a) compensating effort, b) competition tendency, c) feeling confidence about being successful, d) domination, superiority, e) desire to learn, f) regular and continuous working, h) fearlessness, i) flexibility, j) focusing, k) goal setting, l) independency, m) internalizing, n) insisting, tenacity, o) preferring difficult duties, ö) feeling pride and honor from productivity, p) self-control, r) obtaining a footing. These factors define AKUT KOE in terms of the persons having high SC, EI scores, suitable for the teamwork and having high leadership characteristics.

The reason for the individuals to take place in AKUT KOE Team is strengthening the image of AKUT created in the community by belonging to AKUT and by the effort given in order to realize its mission and the social benefit created instead of achieving success individually. This can be likened to psychological relieves of a person's success having asthma attack after placing to a known hospital and having the belief of the individual and his/her relatives for being safe by trusting the hospital for favorable outcomes.

5. Emotional Intelligence

In the years of 1920s, EI (Emotional Intelligence) was first stated by Thorndike's social intelligence approach and becoming conceptualized with Salovey and Mayer (1990), has found its current known and corresponding state in science and business world with the studies done by Goleman (1995, 2007). As is, EI has been correlated with the individual himself/herself and to recognize the feelings of the others and to develop empathy with them, self-motivation and motivating the others, developing the self-confidence, skill and competence to be able to manage the feelings in the existing

situation and in the relations enabled (Ardahan, 2012b). Original of EI scale, the scale developed from the work of Schutte et al., (2006); consists of four dimensions as follows: "Emotional Evaluation" defining the individual that he/she is aware of his/her own feelings, "Positive Emotional Management" defining the empathy, "Empathic Sensitiveness" defining the empathy developed with the others and "Positive Usage of the Feelings" defining the manageability of self and others' feelings. As the researches done, it was discovered that individuals having high EI can fictionalize meaningful and satiated relations in family, social and business lives, they lead to success level defining them in their relations (faster), that they are more productive and prolific, they are loved and respected by the people surrounding them, that are able to move rapidly upwards in their careers. For this reason, importance has increased for the employment of individuals having high EI scores in every environment where teamwork, leadership, problem solving, and interaction between the individuals are necessary (Doğan and Demiral, 2007).

Search and rescue activity is the saving operation of survivor individual(s) who are encountered of dying or becoming injured because of a disaster or accident arising from human/nature and cannot be escaped from the existing situation by himself/herself. It is a dangerous work and both search and rescue stage needs a serious organizing, planning, problem solving and risk management. There are internationally approved basic values and ethical infrastructures of Search and Rescue activity. Search Rescue activity is mostly realized in complicated and nervous environments. It is done by the specialist persons who do not run after personal interests, it requires teamwork and it is done completely by being volunteered, it seriously requires problem solving, leadership, risk management, the subject in the operation having the first priority is to rescue of the survivor (TUBITAK). The ones who participate and manage such an important activity must have high emotional intelligence. Therefore, AKUT volunteers must be in a development to be able to understand the feelings of themselves and the others to be able to develop empathy with them and to be able to manage their own feelings as well as the feelings of the others in their daily lives, while they are active in their volunteerism operation and in extraordinary conditions (during the operation).

EI concept is also defined as the entire skills influencing/determining the success expectations in the life of the individual to a large extent (Doğan and Demiral, 2007). Success concept mentioned here is not only having career, status, richness, measurable material values, but at the same time it defines the feeling of the individual to feel happier and better, to have more pleasure from living and qualitatively be satisfied about the results obtained (Doğan, 2005)

Generally, when volunteerism is viewed from being the volunteer in AKUT specially, it is a process requiring devotion to a mission and to perform quality efforts in order to realize that mission, needs the focusing to the opportunity in creating added value to the mission by the skills and abilities of the persons by disregarding personal differences, to use the energy for the mission by staying away from personal ego, familiarity to teamwork at high level, skill to solve problems and leadership

competence and volunteered career journeys of the individuals is also a process having positive influence on EI. Together with this, having low EI of the individual and/or being in interaction with the persons having low EI in the volunteerism processes can cause the individual to give up from sustaining volunteerism. Persons having high EI are defined as the "matured person" in our community. It is expected to have positive influence on EI and LS of the individuals having activities in volunteerism and naturally these must be high.

In the light of all these explanations, the purpose of this study is to meet SC, LS, AP and EI levels of the individuals with the volunteers participating in AKUT KOE as well as the ones who have not participated in any volunteerism activity through their lives or have been volunteer previously but could not continue to be the volunteer because of the negativities encountered.

6. Method

6.1 Research Model and Sample

This study is a descriptive research and it has two different samples. The first one consists of 208 persons from the total of 420 persons taking place in AKUT KOE and these persons have replied to the survey forms that were sent to them as e-mail. The second one consists of the persons who have not participated in any volunteerism activity in anywhere all through their lives or have done volunteerism but could not continue volunteerism because some problems. It is difficult to determine their number and for this reason, this group consists of 138 persons determined by way of simple random sampling by being close/suitable to AKUT Profile.

6.2 Data Collection Tool

In the study, electronic survey was applied for AKUT KOE and face-to-face survey was applied for the other volunteers. Together with obtaining demographic information of the individuals, both survey forms have included Social Capital Scale (SCS) developed by Onyx and Bullen (2000) and adapted to Turkish by Ardahan (2012), Achievement Perception Scale (APS) developed by Bilgin and Kaynak (2008), Life Satisfaction Scale (LSS) developed by Diener et al., (1985) and having its Turkish adaptation done by Köker (1991), Emotional Intelligence Scale (EIS) developed by Schutte et al., and used by Chan (2004; 2006). The clauses in the evaluation of EIS, LSS and APS evaluation have been weighted as (1- Strongly Disagree,..., 5- Strongly Agree), in SCS (1- Definitely No..., 4- Definitely Yes).

6.3 Data Analysis

Together with defining statistics, Independent Samples test (t) has been used in the analysis of the data in the study in determining the difference between the two groups and the results were evaluated at the level of 0.05 relevance.

6.4 Reliability Values of Scales

Cronbach Alpha values of the scales have been found as SCS (Cronbach's Alpha=0.806), EUS (Cronbach's Alpha=0.934), APS (Cronbach's Alpha=0.605) and LSS (Cronbach's Alpha=0.854) and they are within the limits of validity in four scales.

7. Findings

Demographic data consisting of people taking place in AKUT KOE, people who have never been volunteer throughout their lives or given up from being volunteer because of the boredoms encountered are given in Table-1. As it is seen from the Table, great majority of the participants consists of the individuals who are male, bachelor, under 30 years of age, had/having education at university level or more. This is valid for both AKUT volunteers and for the ones who are not volunteers. In addition to this, incomes of AKUT volunteers are more when compared with the ones who are not volunteers. Main reason of this is arising from the fact that important part of AKUT volunteers are working.

Table 1: Demographic Data belonging to the Participants

Demographics Variables	AKUT		Non Volunteers		Total	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Man	162	77,9	111	80,4	273	78,9
Women	46	22,1	27	19,6	73	21,1
Married	90	43,3	18	13,0	108	31,2
Single	118	56,7	120	87,0	238	68,8
30 years old and below	80	38,5	122	88,4	202	58,4
31-40 years old	72	34,6	9	6,5	81	23,4
41 years old and more	56	26,9	7	5,1	63	18,2
High School or below	46	22,1	15	10,9	61	17,6
University or upper	162	77,9	123	89,1	285	82,4
350 \$ and below	40	19,2	96	69,6	136	39,3
351-700 \$	56	26,9	29	21,0	85	24,6
701-1050 \$	60	28,8	13	9,4	73	21,1
1051\$ and more	52	25,0	0	0,0	52	15,0
Total	208	100,0	138	100,0	246	100,0

1 ABD\$ = 3.0 TL in 2016 March

Comparisons of AKUT Volunteers and Non-volunteers with various psychosocial parameters are given in Table-2. As seen from the Table, comparisons have been done with SCS, EIS, APS and LSS and in every sub-dimension of the scales, there is statistically meaningful difference between the scores of AKUT Volunteers and scores of Non-volunteers and differences are all in favor of AKUT Volunteers in all of them.

Despite of the fact that AKUT Volunteers have higher score than Non-volunteers in Participation to Local Community from SCS sub-dimension, it was expected to have this rate higher. Even though Participation to Local Community is formed by the clauses explaining the inclusion of the individual to the issues of the place where he/she

lives and to take place voluntarily in the solution of them just like in the volunteerism in AKUT, AKUT Volunteers do not include themselves so much in the events in their own environment requiring volunteerism. In addition to this, individual's Social Awareness and Taking Initiative in the Social Issues of the same individuals are considerably high and this supports AKUT Volunteers largely as the serious leisure time activity. Even though important part of AKUT volunteers say that they do not take place in the activities of Non-governmental Organizations, each one of them is volunteer in AKUT and this is not seem to them as the membership of NGO. For them, AKUT Volunteers has more of Life Satisfaction rather than NGO membership. Together with this, Social Security Feeling of AKUT Volunteers is lower than the Feelings of Safety neighborhood; they have considerably high scores in the subjects of Tolerance to Difference, Belonging to somewhere.

Table 2: Comparison of AKUT Volunteers and Non-Volunteers

Psychosocial Parameters	AKUT Volunteers	Non Volunteers	t
	X ± SD	X ± SD	
Social Capital Scales			
Participation in the Local Community	2,96 ± 0,84	2,03 ± 1,02	9,223*
Being member of non-governmental organizations	2,88 ± 1,26	2,07 ± 1,22	5,919*
Being representative of social context	3,55 ± 0,83	3,17 ± 1,03	3,777*
Taking Initiative in the Social Issues	3,86 ± 0,38	3,27 ± 0,97	7,879*
Feelings of Safety neighborhood	3,68 ± 0,83	3,26 ± 1,11	4,056*
Trust to others	2,83 ± 0,96	2,61 ± 1,09	1,963*
Neighborhood Connections	3,31 ± 0,64	3,03 ± 0,94	3,395*
Tolerance of Diversity	3,75 ± 0,66	3,29 ± 1,09	4,891*
Belonging to somewhere	3,73 ± 0,55	3,42 ± 0,91	4,002*
Emotional Intelligence Scale			
Emotional Assessment	4,04 ± 0,62	3,76 ± 1,06	3,076*
Emphatic Sensitiveness	4,12 ± 0,64	3,73 ± 1,00	4,367*
Positive Emotional Management	4,05 ± 0,62	3,76 ± 0,97	3,453*
Utilization Of Emotions Positively	4,20 ± 0,65	3,74 ± 1,10	4,897*
Achievement Perception			
	3,37 ± 0,76	3,11 ± 0,95	2,855*
Life Satisfaction			
	3,53 ± 0,51	3,27 ± 1,00	3,167*

Activities that the participants involve during their leisure times are given in Table-3. As it can be seen from the Table, while nature sports constitute a dominant rate in sportive activities of AKUT Volunteers, team sports come into prominence in non-volunteers. In addition to this, while the sports done in the fitness centers are the second preference of non-volunteers, second preference of AKUT Volunteers is the water sports. Together with this, in non-sport activities, while non-volunteers prefer passive leisure time, there is an active nature in AKUT volunteers. While the first three preferences of non-volunteers are resting at home, doing shopping and surfing in the internet, AKUT volunteers prefer to be with friends, to go to concerts and to be together with the family.

Table 3: Activities done by the Participants in their Leisure Times

Leisure Activities	AKUT Volunteers		Non Volunteers	
	n	%	n	%
Sportive Activities				
Outdoor Sports (like Mountaineering, rock climbing).	82	78,8	36	26,1
Water Sports (Like swimming, canoe, sailing)	35	33,7	35	25,4
Fitness Sports (Fitness, Step Aerobics, Plates, Squash)	22	21,2	37	26,8
Recreational Sports in Parks	19	18,3	13	9,4
Team Sports (Like Football, basketball, volleyball)	17	16,3	58	42,0
Motor Sports (Like Moto cross, off road)	13	12,5	11	8,0
Individual Sports (Like archery, athletics)	12	11,5	9	6,5
Folk Dance	10	9,6	9	6,5
Weather Sports (Like Sky Diving, paragliding)	8	7,7	7	5,1
Racket Sports (like Tennis, Badminton)	7	6,7	19	13,8
Struggle Sports (Like Wrestling, Karate, Taekwondo)	6	5,8	11	8,0
Non-Sports Activities	n	%	n	%
Be in with friends	74	71,2	54	39,1
Going to some concert	71	68,3	61	44,2
Being with family	60	57,7	60	43,5
Internet surfing	57	54,8	77	55,8
Going to cinema	45	43,3	68	49,3
Time spending in Social Media	45	43,3	37	26,8
Watching TV-Video-Film	42	40,4	63	45,7
Going to Theatre	37	35,6	39	28,3
Going for shopping	21	20,2	78	56,5
Resting in home	19	18,3	80	58,0

8. Conclusion

In this study, comparisons of SC, LS, AP and EI levels have been done for the volunteer individuals taking place in AKUT KOE and the individuals who have never been in the activity voluntarily in any place throughout their lives or the ones could not continue the volunteerism in any way because of the negativities.

Difference between the individuals in AKUT KOE and non-volunteers is largely arising from the characteristics of the individuals, their social relations, paradigms and life-styles. The most apparent reflection of this is while AKUT volunteers are in the active sports life; non-volunteer individuals generally prefer passive life. This difference was discovered in Ardahan and Turgut's (2013) study doing the comparison of LSs belonging to the ones doing hunting and fishing and the ones not doing these sports and this was also discovered in Ardahan's (2012c) study for the comparison of LS and IEs of the ones doing and not doing the nature sports. LSs and IEs of the ones doing an activity are resulting higher when compared with the ones not doing that activity.

It is one of the realities discovered in SC, LS literature that SC value and LS level are increased with the social interaction to be created between the individuals by attending to the entertainment of individuals' club, to the activities organized in order to fulfill the requirements of the religion individual believes, evening entertainment

included with business, social life and family environment, sportive, cultural, social reactive activities being included actively or passively alone and/or with the others. In addition to this, it is indicated by many researchers such as Ibrahim and Cordes (2000), Putnam (2001), Sirgy and Cornwell (2002), Brown and Ferris (2007); Wang and Graddy (2008), Paik and Navarre-Jackson (2011), Ardahan (2014a) that attending volunteerism activities has more positive influence on SC when compared to many other factors. In addition to these, it was discovered that environment and feeling of confidence, all kinds of relations and interactions based on trust (Wang and Graddy, 2008), assuming responsibility by the individual to represent the others and fictionalizing relationship with them (Ostrom, 2000), developing healthy neighborhood relationship (Larsen et al., 2004), being included in the civil society (Reimer, 2008; Ostrom, 2000) have positive influence on SC and LS. These conclusions verify that AKUT volunteers in the existing research have higher scores than non-volunteer ones in all sub-dimensions of LSS and SCS and this statistically confirms the meaning of difference between them. By its structure, AKUT is a voluntary NGO helping the others during their difficult times and it needs to be the member to that NGO in order to be the volunteer there. Together with this, the feeling of the volunteers taking place in AKUT KOE to help the others in social boredoms, in natural disasters such as fire, flood and earthquake, having higher scores than non-volunteer ones also in the normal times in sub-dimensions of "Participating in the Local Management", "Taking Initiative in Social Issues" and "Social Representation" for the improvement and more efficient management for the place of living can be derived as defined by Briggs et al., (2010) because individuals have the value for "a motivation focused on the others" more than non-volunteer ones. In addition to this, becoming a member in the NGO established in order to realize a mission they believe requires sense of belonging. For this reason, sense of belonging of the volunteers taking place in AKUT KOE for the volunteerism work perceived by them as the life style and the serious leisure time activity rather than the membership can be higher than non-volunteer ones. Together with these, as it is discovered in the study of Ardahan (2013), in the event of having the approval of this difference by the individuals taking place in life with the differences such as different language, religion, education, life style, having them being more tolerant for the difference in the public sites they live, work and they take place during their leisure times or in the re-creative areas, having the individuals supporting the same mission together under the roof of AKUT and having their support to the needers in emergencies by cooperating with them can provide individuals to be more tolerant to difference in the dimension of "Tolerance to Difference" than non-volunteer persons.

Also in the study of Hunter and Linn (1980), it was discovered that the individuals at the age of 65 and above and working as the volunteer have higher LS than non-volunteers, they also have higher will to live, and determination and they have lower depression, anxiety and mental disorders (somatization). These results match up with all results of the existing research. In addition to these, in the study of Ardahan (2013), it was stated that living meaningful and satiated neighborhood

relationship, being tolerant to differences has positive influence on individuals' LS. Here, AKUT volunteers have higher "Neighborhood Relationship" and "Tolerance to Difference" level and these may cause that volunteers have higher LS levels than non-volunteer persons.

Like many authors such as Luthans (1994), Schemerhorn et al. (1994), Sirgy and Cornwell (2002), Özer and Karabulut (2003), Ardahan (2014a); other than many factors such as income, age, working, healthy neighborhood relationship, physical, mental health state, existence of financial possibilities, social status, instrumental comfort, meaningful and satiated marriage, relations in the family, business and social life Bjornskov (2003) has defended that there is an important relation between the other LS and individual's way of perception for the life, his/her paradigm and the things done by himself/herself. In addition to the ones done by the person himself/herself, also the things done for the others have influence his/her LS along with his/her self-belief. These expressions support the result that existing working has higher LS for AKUT volunteers when compared with the non-volunteers.

When the success is defined as the realization of the objectives approved by the individual and defined by the individual and/or by the others by using the resources efficiently and productively (McClelland, 1985; Ardahan, 2014b) being in AKUT KOE and to interfere to the persons in emergencies shall cause the individuals to feel the perception of success stronger than non-volunteer persons. In fact, the results of the existing research have the characteristic to support this situation. When this result is interpreted more comprehensively; it is seen that AKUT has been structured, managed by complying "managerial reality depending on organizations' qualified employment creation for their success in the competition process" valid for all organizations including the NGOs defined as public sector, private sector and third sector and it has the competent persons taking role in all of its operations.

There are many studies indicating that EI is important in leadership (George, 2000), marriage (Gotmann 1993), business life (Goleman, 1996) and every place where life paces on and the individuals having high EI are more successful in leadership, marriage, business and social life (Ardahan, 2012b; Doğan and Demiral, 2007). In the study of Granvold (1994), he has defended that communication skills are generated from EIs of in the individuals and it has positive influence on the happiness and success of the individuals. In addition to this, in the study done by Schutte et al., (2001) revealed that individuals having high social skill levels also have high EI levels and they are successful in cooperation, teamwork, being the part of a mission and in close emotional and social relations. It was revealed in many studies that there is a positive correlation between volunteerism and IE (Hughes and Terrell (2011). All these mentioned things verify the result in the existing research that the volunteers taking place in AKUT KOE must have higher EI values than non-volunteer ones.

In conclusion, life styles, the way of using leisure times, participated activities, SC, EI, LS and AP levels of the volunteer individuals taking place in AKUT KOE and the individuals who have never attended volunteerism activity throughout their lives

or do not continue volunteerism activity because of the boredoms encountered are different. This difference is in favor of AKUT Volunteers. In other words, EI, LS, SC and APs of the individuals preferring volunteerism as the life style are high when compared to non-volunteer persons. For this reason, individuals must be motivated to be the volunteer in every moment of living in the families, social and business world's friend environment, in school life, social media and volunteerism must be structured in the way to take place in their lives and to become the life style.

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